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ABBREVIATIONS

IP: Intellectual Property

IPR: Intellectual Property Right

WIPO: World Intellectual Property Organization

USPTO: United States Patent and Trademark Office

PDT: Patent, Design and Trademark

TRIPS: Agreement On the Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights

UDHR: Universal Declaration on Human Rights

WTO: World Trade Organization

LDC: Least Developed Country

DoI: Department of Industry

TM: Trademark

KII: Key Informant Interview

FTC: Federal Trade Commission

CPC: Consumer Protection Cooperation

OECD: Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development

SADC: Southern African Development Community

TRIPS: Agreement On the Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights

CHAPTER - I

1.1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

In the modern era, intellectual property rights play a significant role on trade of every nation. No one would like their ideas to be copied without their permission or without having the credits. Just like the movable and immovable properties, the owners of intellectual properties would want to protect their properties. Also the intellectual properties are rather unique than tangible properties because it is created by using human creativity.

Trademark infringement is the unauthorized use of a trademark or service mark on or in connection with goods and/or services in a manner that is likely to cause confusion, deception, or mistake about the source of the goods and/or services.¹ History reveals that both trademark and consumer laws were evolved with the sole aim of protecting consumers and safeguarding ‘consumers’ interest.²

The most common trademarks are brand or product names, logos, slogans, and combinations of such marks.³ For example; The word ‘NIKE’ alone is a trademark and the word ‘NIKE’ in distinctive font is another trademark. The classic Nike swoosh graphic and the slogan “JUST DO IT” are also individual trademarks.⁴ Additionally, any combination of these individual marks would also be considered a unique trademark on its own.

Trademarks are not limited to words and designs. Sounds, colors, smells, textures, shapes, motions, and the appearance of products, packaging, or places of business can also be protectable by trademark law. For example, Owens Corning has a trademark on the color pink in relation to fiberglass insulation. Metro-Goldwyn-Mayer (MGM) has a trademark on the

¹ United States Patent and Trademark Office, About Trademark Infringement, <https://www.uspto.gov/page/about-trademark-infringement> (accessed on 12th August, 2022).

² Lisa P. Lukose, *Consumer Protection Vis A Vis Trademark Law*, <https://clap.nls.ac.in/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/CONSUMER-PROTECTION-VIS-A.pdf> (accessed on 12th August, 2022).

³ DYLAN O ADAMS, PATENT ATTORNEY, PATENTS DEMYSTIFIED: AN INSIDER’S GUIDE TO PROTECTING IDEAS AND INVENTIONS, (2nd edition), American Bar Association, USA, 2015).

⁴ Types of Intellectual Property, <http://www.patentsdemystified.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/Patents-Demystified-Chapter-1-Sample.pdf> (accessed on October 17, 2022).

sound of a roaring lion that is part of the company graphic it presents at the beginning of MGM films.⁵

Every person is a consumer of goods and services and as a corollary the term ‘consumer’ can virtually be equated with the term ‘human being’, every person remains a consumer from cradle to grave. We live in a consumer society surrounded by many goods and services, and the decision to purchase a particular good or service depends in large part on the trademarks.⁶

In most trademark cases, infringement is established by showing that the defendant’s use is likely to confuse an appreciable number of consumers into believing that the plaintiff is the source of the defendant’s products, or sponsors or is somehow affiliated with the defendant or its products.⁷ There is no need to show that consumers are actually confused; a significant likelihood is enough for liability.⁸

Making the same choice, but disabling the consumer from informing others about the product or causing them to misinform others, which may create problems. Confused consumers are likely to confuse other consumers when spreading word-of-mouth by passing on too much inaccurate or irrelevant decision-making information.⁹

The notion of ‘consumer protection’ is aiming at the protection of the interests of the consumers.¹⁰ Consumer protection laws thus primarily safeguard the rights of consumers by preventing unfair trade practices.¹¹ Similarly, trademark law too tries to protect consumers by preventing deception in the market by a number of ways. The essential function of trademark is that it is a badge of origin.¹² The advertising function relates to the cachet or aura which the

⁵ Id.

⁶ Lukose, Supra 2.

⁷ Moseley v. V Secret Catalogue, U.S.R 418, 123 (S. C. 1115, 2003).

⁸ J. THOMAS MCCARTHY, TRADEMARKS AND UNFAIR COMPETITION, 3:5 (4th ed), (2009).

⁹ Vincent-Wayne Mitchell, *Marketing Causes and Implications of Consumer Confusion*, Journal of Product & Brand Management, VOL 8, University of Sydney, (2020).

¹⁰ Lukose, Supra 2.

¹¹ Consumer Protection Act, 1986, Section 2 (r) unfair trade practice" means a trade practice which, for the purpose of promoting the sale, use or supply of any goods or for the provision of any service, adopts any unfair method or unfair or deceptive practice.

¹² DAVID KITCHIN, DAVID LLEWELYN ET. AL, KERLY’S LAW OF TRADE MARKS AND TRADE NAMES, (8th Ed), Sweet & Maxwell, London, (2007).

consumers associate with the marks. The trademark thus serves to reduce the search cost by assuring quality of the product and acts as a symbol representing the goodwill of the business.¹³

1.2 Statement of Problems

Trademark is a form of IP like a mark, image, logo or anything that represents a business which is exclusive to that particular business. Just like tangible properties, the intangible properties also need to be registered following the due process of law.

Every creation requires time, energy and effort. The time involved varies greatly between projects. Copying the already existing products' formula and deceiving the general public is an easy way out to earn money. A likelihood of confusion exists when an allegedly infringing trademark is likely to cause an appreciable number of reasonably prudent purchasers to be confused as to the source or origin of the products or services it is used to identify.

1. Whether trademark infringed goods have affected the consumers?
2. Whether the existing laws address the issues of infringed TM adequately?
3. Whether the existing laws have been implemented properly?

1.3 Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that trademark infringement increases confusion in consumers.

1.4 Objective of The Study

Despite being careful and the existing numbers of acts, plans and policies being implemented, the trademark infringement has been increasing. Therefore, the researcher has based the study on the very issue and the major objectives behind the study are listed down:

1. To survey about the effect of TM infringement on consumers.
2. To know about the foreign company's concerns wishing to enter Nepali market.
3. To study the laws related to TM infringement and its implementation.

¹³ Lukose, Supra 2.

1.5 Significance of The Study

The increase of duplication and infringement of trademark has been a very serious issue in Nepalese market affecting the general public. So this study is to focus on the existence and impact of the trademark infringement along with protection of consumer. It includes related major legal provisions and some suggestions from the researcher at the end. Anyone willing to know about the contemporary status of infringement of trademark vis a vis consumer protection via affiliated legal instruments can find this research paper helpful. It can include; students, teachers, creators, researchers etc. Few bullets of the significance of the paper are listed below:

- The paper focuses on the overall status of infringement of trademark vis a vis consumer's right.
- This paper can be useful to the concerned parties who are willing to gain more knowledge on existing market condition and the rights of the consumers as mentioned in the laws.
- Since the research is done using both doctrinal and non- doctrinal method of study keeping both perspective side by side which is not so common, it can be helpful to other researchers in future.

1.6 Literature Review

A well-structured literature review was conducted so as to characterize a logical flow and comprehensive view of the previous study of this topic. For the same purpose, researcher tried to collect relevant books and journals. Among gathered literature, few of the very useful during the study are as follows:

The Economic Structure of Intellectual Property Law, Harvard University Press, William M. Landes Richard A. Posner, 2003.

This book takes a fresh look at the most dynamic area of American law today, comprising the fields of copyright, patent, trademark, trade secrecy, publicity rights, and misappropriation. Topics range from copyright in private letters to defensive patenting of business methods, from moral rights in the visual arts to the banking of trademarks, from the impact of the court of patent appeals to the management of Mickey Mouse. The history and political science of

intellectual property law, the challenge of digitization, the many statutes and judge-made doctrines, and the interplay with antitrust principles are all examined. The treatment is both positive (oriented toward understanding the law as it is) and normative (oriented to the reform of the law). Previous analyses have tended to overlook the paradox that expanding intellectual property rights can effectively reduce the amount of new intellectual property by raising the creators' input costs. Those analyses have also failed to integrate the fields of intellectual property law. They have failed as well to integrate intellectual property law with the law of physical property, overlooking the many economic and legal-doctrinal parallels. This book demonstrates the fundamental economic rationality of intellectual property law, but is sympathetic to critics who believe that in recent decades Congress and the courts have gone too far in the creation and protection of intellectual property rights.

Trademark and Unfair Competition; Law and Policy, 5th Edition, 2018.

The many strands of trademark and unfair competition doctrine are organized into a coherent conceptual framework consisting of a brief examination of foundational concepts, followed by thorough treatments of the law on (1) the creation of trademark rights; and (2) the scope & enforcement of trademark rights and some related causes of action. The traditional case-and-note format is enhanced by problems that help students understand intricate key topics. Trademarks and Unfair Competition features many issues related to online commerce, such as cybersquatting, keyword advertising, the relationship between trademarks and domain names, and the potential secondary liability of online auction websites such as eBay. International as well as domestic issues are thoroughly explored. Comprehensive coverage of trade dress protection is integrated with issues of word mark protection. It is a comprehensive two-volume collection of leading articles in trademark and unfair competition law spans almost a century and three continents, bringing together the most influential and significant scholarly work in this exciting field contributed by B. Beebe, L. Bently, R.S. Brown Jr., W. Cornish, R. Dreyfuss, A. Kur, J. Litman, R. Posner, F. Schechter and many more.

Intellectual property rights in the WTO and developing countries, Jayashree Watal, Kluwer Law International, 2002 she provides a detailed understanding of how TRIPS was negotiated at the Uruguay Round, how various countries have implemented it so far, and how the WTO monitors compliance. In addition to that the author, explains how developing

countries can interpret TRIPS to their best advantage, and how to ensure that the 'constructive ambiguity' that characterizes the agreement remains flexible.

Agreement Between the World Intellectual Property Organization and the World Trade Organization. World Intellectual Property Organization, 1996.

The book contains the provisions mentioned in the TRIPS Agreement of the Paris Convention (1967), the Berne Convention (1971), the Rome Convention (1961), the Treaty on Intellectual Property in Respect of Integrated Circuits (1989), the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade 1994 (GATT) and the WTO Dispute Settlement Understanding (1994).

Consumer Protection Vis a Vis Trademark Law.

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Trademark: Infringement and Passing Off

Trademark: Infringement and Passing off is an article prepared by Anamika Bhaduri; Student, 5th Year, B.A LL.B (Hons.) National Law Institute University, Bhopal. It has the basic introduction, objectives, importance based on the Indian Trademark Law, 1999.

Passing Off and Infringement of Trademarks - India

This article comprises of the principles of passing off and infringement action under the Trademarks Act, 1999. It provides for what acts constitute passing off and infringement of trademarks, what are the remedies available, who can sue and be sued and the defenses available in case of trademark violation. The paper also discusses the factors to be considered in case of passing off and infringement action along with different judicial pronouncements given by Indian Courts.

The Role of Consumer Surveys in Trademark Infringement: Empirical Evidence From The Federal Courts

Robert C Bird; University of Connecticut UConn · Department of Marketing JD, Boston University School of Law; MBA, Boston University Graduate School of Management, Joel H. Steckel; Professor of Marketing, Stern School of Business, New York University have prepared an article to focus on the role of consumer surveys to know about trademark infringement gathering data through courts.

Securing Intellectual Property Rights, New Business Age, Sanjeev Sharma and Sabin Jung Pande. It is an article focusing from the meaning of IP to the status of IP with the statistics as well as legal provisions. It has emphasized on the weaknesses of Nepal on failing to register various of Nepalese products in global market and the opportunities missed because of the very reason.

The above mentioned books, journals and articles have been a great help in my seminar report, however my report is different from the above mentioned literatures. It is a new and relevant research on the topic.

1.7 Limitation of The Study

This seminar report was prepared with academic purpose for the partial fulfilment of BA.LLB, Department of Law, TU. It is limited to the trademark infringement and the impact of it upon consumers. The non-doctrinal data is limited to the responses and brief analysis by the researcher on the data. The doctrinal data of the report is limited to the literature reviews of the report as mentioned in 1.6 of the report.

The time limit to conduct the research to prepare this report is as approved by the Central Department of Law, Nepal Law Campus, Exhibition Road, Bhrikutimandap.

1.8 Research Methodology

1.8.1 Study Area

Trademark infringement is related to registered rights, and passing off related to unregistered rights of a person or company, entity, etc. In simple words when the trademark has been registered by the owner and infringement happens, then it becomes a suit for infringement, but if the trademark has not been registered by the owner and infringement happens, then it

becomes a case of passing off.¹⁴ The seminar paper is strictly limited to trademark infringement and how it affects the general consumers in Nepal. It does not deal with the idea of passing off of trademark in data collected and analyzed.

1.8.2 Study Design

The methodology of study is primarily non-doctrinal where the research data has been collected through primary sources. Also, the data found through doctrinal sources has been included, studied and analyzed. This is a descriptive and analytical study effects of trademark infringement on consumers and businesses. The research method designed to achieve the objectives of this seminar contains study design, population and sample, data collection procedure, tool for analysis and methods of analysis and presentations.

1.8.3 Sources of Data

1.8.3.1 Primary Sources and Secondary Sources.

The primary data was collected through online and physical survey. The respondents of the survey are law experts, lawyers, victims and the general public. In order to fulfill the objectives of the study, case study, 116 samples from the people were taken for the opinion survey. The secondary data of this research were collected from different sources like published and unpublished reports, various books written scholars, newspaper articles and various websites.

1.8.3.2: Qualitative Data and Quantitative Data.

Physical as well as Online survey related to the topic functioned as quantitative data in the seminar report that helped researcher to systematically measure variables and test hypothesis. Secondary sources of data and the information gained through Key Informant Interview (KII) functioned as qualitative data that allowed researcher to explore concepts and experiences in more detail.

1.8.3.3 Sample Design

¹⁴ Concept of Passing off in Trademark Act, 1999, Shubhangi Sharma, https://blog.ipleaders.in/trademark-passing-off/#Difference_between_Passing_Off_and_Infringement_of_Trademark (Accessed on August 17, 2022).

The population of the survey for quantitative data collection was conducted by the researcher is 116 [101 online responses and 15 field responses]. It is a non-probability sampling and the majority of respondents are from age 18-28.

1.8.3.4 Research Tools and Techniques

For the purpose of this research, I developed a questionnaire and conducted survey whose respondents were from all age groups and different fields. The information of the respondents was kept confidential. Also, key informant interview (KII) and Case Studies were done to achieve the objective of this Seminar Rules of Citation The researcher has followed uniform rule of citation whereas bibliography is done according to uniform rule of citation.

1.8.6 Data Analysis

Descriptive method of data analysis of the non-doctrinal data generated from online and physical survey has been used in the seminar report.

1.8.7 Research Ethics

The basic principle of research ethics i.e., confidentiality of the respondents and the integrity of the data has been duly followed while carrying out the research. Similarly, no any harm has been inflicted upon victims or any other person while carrying out the research.

1.8.8 Rules of citation

The Uniform Citation Style has been followed by the researcher as prescribed in the Manual Of Uniform Citation Style For Legal Research by Dr. Bal Bahadur Mukhiya and Dr. DN Parajuli.

1.8.8 Validity and Reliability

The seminar report has been prepared using the literatures as well as the citations mentioned in the report but the report itself is a new and unique from all the sources mentioned. The data collected by the researchers are from real people. any hoax or fake data has not been presented in the seminar report.

1.9 Organization of the Study

The organization of the study is as follow:

Chapter I: Introduction,

The first chapter includes the general background of the study along with the problems and objectives followed by literature review. Then the method of research, significance, limitation organization of study and other introductory headings complete this chapter.

Chapter II: Conceptual Framework of the study

After basic introduction we have the conceptual framework of Trademark Infringement and Consumer Protection where the meaning, definitions, history, functions and classifications are discussed to get detailed idea of the study.

Chapter III: Legal Framework of the study

Since the study has been conducted by a law student it covers the legal aspects too. Both national and international legal instruments have been addressed in this chapter. It also includes cases decided by various levels of national and international courts.

Chapter IV: Data Presentation

The forth chapter of the study includes the data presentation of the researcher collected through physical as well as online survey.

Chapter V: Data Analysis

The fifth chapter of the seminar report has the analysis of the data collected through surveys along with the researcher's and KII's opinion.

Chapter VI: Findings, Conclusion and Suggestions

The final chapter includes the findings, conclusion of the study and some suggestions from the researcher's side.

CHAPTER – II

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Concept and Meaning of Trademark and Consumer Protection.

In the case of *Bristol-Myers Squibb v. Paranova* (1996)¹⁵, it was held by the Advocate General that; In so far as the trademark protects the interest of its proprietor by enabling him to prevent competitors from taking unfair advantage of his commercial reputation, the exclusive right conferred on the proprietor are said, in the language of the Court’s case law, to constitute the specific subject matter of the trademark. In so far as the trademark protects the interest of consumer by acting as a guarantee that all goods bearing the mark are of the same origin, this is known in the Court’s terminology, as the essential function of the trademark. These two aspects of trademark protection are of course two sides of the same coin.

Trademark law protects a trademark owner’s exclusive rights to use the mark, thereby preventing any unlawful use of the mark by an infringer.

Consumer interests can also be protected by promoting competition in the markets which directly and indirectly serve consumers, consistent with economic efficiency, but this topic is treated in competition law.¹⁶ Consumer protection laws are a form of government regulation, which aim to protect the rights of consumers. For example, a government may require businesses to disclose detailed information about products—particularly in areas where safety or public health is an issue, such as food. Consumer protection is linked to the idea of “consumer rights” (that consumers have various rights as consumers), and to the formation of consumer organizations, which help consumers make better choices in the marketplace and get help with consumer complaints.¹⁷

¹⁵ *Bristol-Myers Squibb and Others v. Paranova*, C.M.L.R. 1151 (CC, 1996).

¹⁶ Consumer Protection Law, Consumer Protection, 2014, <http://consumer-protection-law-blog.com/> (accessed on October 30, 2022).

¹⁷ Consumer Protection, February 12, 2014, <http://consumer-protection-law-blog.com/> (accessed on October 30, 2022).

We live in a consumer society surrounded by many goods and services, and the decision to purchase a particular good or service depends in large part on the trademarks.¹⁸ Similarly, trademark law too tries to protect consumers by preventing deception in the market by a number of ways. The essential function of trademark is that it is a badge of origin.¹⁹ The trademark thus serves to reduce the search cost by assuring quality of the product and acts as a symbol representing the goodwill of the business. When the subject of trademark is approached from a consumer perspective, one can find grave lacunae in the existing trademark system which directly or indirectly resulting in the consumer detriment.²⁰ Over the years, a substantial statutory framework has been developed to design various measures to protect consumers. On the other hand, the relevance of trading malpractices, the sale of counterfeit goods, lack of consumer education and awareness and so on remain rampant.²¹

2.2 Definition of Trademark and Consumer Protection.

A consumer is defined as someone who acquires goods or services for direct use or ownership rather than for resale or use in production and manufacturing.²²

"Consumer" means a person or institution that consumes or uses any goods or services.²³

Indian Consumer Protection Act, 2019 defines consumer as; "consumer" means any person who—

- (i) buys any goods for a consideration which has been paid or promised or partly paid and partly promised, or under any system of deferred payment and includes any user of such goods other than the person who buys such goods for consideration paid or promised or partly paid or partly promised, or under any system of deferred payment, when such use is made with the approval of such person, but does not

¹⁸ HàTh Nguyt Thu, Well-Known Trademark Protection Reference to the Japanese Experience, Final Report in Fulfillment of the Long Term Fellowship 11 (WIPO, 2010).

¹⁹ Llewelyn et. Al. Supra 12.

²⁰ Lukose, Supra 2.

²¹ Id.

²² Van Loo, Rory, *Broadening Consumer Law: Competition, Protection, and Distribution*, NOTRE DAME LAW REVIEW, VOL 95:1, Boston University, Boston (2019).

²³ Consumer Protection Act, Section 2(d), (2075).

include a person who obtains such goods for resale or for any commercial purpose;
or

- (ii) hires or avails of any service for a consideration which has been paid or promised or partly paid and partly promised, or under any system of deferred payment and includes any beneficiary of such service other than the person who hires or avails of the services for consideration paid or promised, or partly paid and partly promised, or under any system of deferred payment, when such services are availed of with the approval of the first mentioned person, but does not include a person who avails of such service for any commercial purpose.²⁴

"Trade-mark" means word, symbol, or picture or a combination thereof to be used by any firm, company or individual in its products or services to distinguish them with the product or services of others.²⁵

The Korean trademark law defines trademark as, "trademark" means any of the following items (hereinafter referred to as "mark") that is used by a person who produces, processes or sells goods as a business, in order to distinguish the goods related to his/her business from those of another person:

- (a) Any sign, letter, figure, three-dimensional shape or the combination thereof or the combination of them and colors;
- (b) Any color that is not combined with others, the combination of colors, any hologram, movement or other item that can be visually recognized;
- (c) Any sound, odor or others that expressed realistically with a sign, letter, figure, or by any other visual means among sounds, odors and others that cannot be recognized visually.²⁶

²⁴ Consumer Protection Act, Section 2(7), (2075).

²⁵ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 2(c), (2022).

²⁶ Trademark Act, Article 2(1), (1990).

2.2.1 Passing Off of trademark

The principle of passing off, i.e. “Nobody has the right to represent his goods as the goods of somebody else”²⁷ was decided in the case of *Perry v Truefitt* (1842).²⁸

In layman terms, passing off occurs when a trader/businessperson/or another person makes a false representation to their customer or consumer to lead them in believing that the goods or services they are delivering are the property of another person.²⁹

The law of passing off prohibits one person from impersonating another’s goods or services. The concept of passing off was not very broad at first, and it has evolved significantly over time. The rule of passing off was originally solely applicable to products. That no single person may misrepresent the goods of others. At a later time, this was extended to include goods, businesses, and services. Passing off was then expanded to include professions and non-trading activities.³⁰ In a Passing off action, the user must prove that the trademark they are using has a distinct identity for the product. However, if someone uses the same thing, it will create confusion in the minds of people and will cause harm to their business reputation.³¹

It is difficult to prove passing off as claimants need to demonstrate that at least some of the public is at risk of confusion between the two businesses. The most important question in Passing off is whether the conduct of the defendants is such as to confuse the public that the business of the defendants is a plaintiff or a cause of confusion between the business activities of the two. This Act of misrepresentation often damages the goodwill of a person or business, causing financial or reputational damage.³²

In a recent case of *S. Syed Mohideen v. P. Sulochana Bai*³³, the Apex Court of the country stated that passing off right is a wider remedy than that of infringement. This

²⁷ *Perry v Truefitt* E.R. 749, (CC, 1842).

²⁸ iPleaders, Shubhangi Sharma, a 5th-year student of BA LLB in Lloyd Law College, Greater Noida, October 15, 2019, <https://blog.ipleaders.in/trademark-passing-off/>, (accessed on November 11, 2022).

²⁹ Taxguru, Passing Off and Infringement of Trademark, <https://taxguru.in/corporate-law/passing-infringement-trademark.html> (accessed on November 10, 2022).

³⁰ Id.

³¹ Id.

³² Sharma, *Supra* 28.

³² Taxguru, *Supra* 29.

³³ *S. Syed Mohideen vs P. Sulochana Bai* AIR 12671,(SC, 2015).

is because the passing off doctrine operates on the general principle that no person is entitled to represent his or her business as the business of another person. The said action of deceit is maintainable for diverse reasons other than that of registered rights which are allocated rights under the Act.³⁴

The Law of Passing-off and infringement is very important for the reputation and goodwill of one's business. If any person finds that his trademark registered or unregistered is being misused, he/she can directly approach the court. A registered trademark is the property of the company. Also, it directly associates with Goodwill, reputation and quality of products. No one can use the same trademark which is in use by other companies. In the same way, passing off arises when it injures the Goodwill of one's business when there is misrepresentation and thirdly in the damages. The remedy provided in both the cases that are in the case of passing off and infringement is generally the same.³⁵

2.3 History of Trademark and Consumer Protection.

The development of trademarks can be traced back to the onset of industrial revolution, which facilitated in the large scale production and distribution of goods.³⁶ With the growth of globalization and e-commerce consumers started identifying their products with that of certain marks and symbols so as to distinguish these products from other similar products in the market.³⁷ Over a prolonged period of usage, the products with particular marks started gaining popularity as well as recognition among consumers of goods and with advertising came the propensity to copy the well-known trademarks or adopt deceptive trademarks to enhance profits and gain unscrupulous financial gain by trading on the reputation of another trade mark.³⁸ Trademarks, or symbols, words, or images, connect products and services to the companies that manufacture them. Modern symbols, such as R, TM, and SM, signify the legal protection, but trademarks have been around for a long

³⁴ Khurana & Khurana Advocates and IP Attorneys, India: Difference Between Passing Off And Infringement Of The Trade Mark <https://www.mondaq.com/india/trademark/902156/difference-between-passing-off-and-infringement-of-the-trade-mark> (accessed on November 10, 2022).

³⁵ Taxguru, Supra 29.

³⁶ Anamika Bhaduri, *Trademark: Infringement And Passing Off*, Student, 5th Year, B.A LL.B (Hons.) National Law Institute University, Bhopal.

³⁷ Id.

³⁸ Id.

time. In fact, the history traces back to Biblical times and earlier.³⁹ The origin of trademarks can be traced back as far as the beginning of the circulation of goods. The history of marks is nearly as old as the histories of mankind and religion. Scientists have come across excavated artifacts from places such as ancient Egypt with various symbols carved thereon for religious and superstitious reasons.⁴⁰

It is nearly impossible to pinpoint exactly when the first trademark came to be, but one of the earliest known examples dates back to 5000 BC like in China and Transylvania, the pottery also showcased the location where the pottery was created, along with the name of the person who manufactured each piece and sometimes the name of the Chinese Emperor in power.⁴¹

Another way to look at the history of trademarks is found in the definition of the word “hieroglyphs.” A Greek Egyptian Hellenistic author, Horapollon, wrote a book titled “Hieroglyphica.” In this book, he stated that hieroglyphs served as ideograms that conveyed ideas, not as elements of the local language. Examples contained within the book became more common and visible in emblematic science. For example, he talked about the Phoenix bird and its meaning. As he described in his book, demotic script was first found as early as 660 BC, at the start of the 26th dynasty.⁴²

The Federal Trade Commission was created on September 26, 1914, when President Woodrow Wilson signed the Federal Trade Commission Act into law. The FTC opened its doors on March 16, 1915. The FTC's mission is to protect consumers and promote competition. As the FTC celebrates its 100th anniversary, our thoughts turn to its unique mission, significant events in Commission history, and its staff, stakeholders and constituents – present and past. The FTC works with foreign competition and consumer protection authority, and cooperates with foreign authorities on enforcement and policy matters through formal and informal agreements. In Europe there are many consumers' organizations. The Regulation on Consumer Protection Cooperation (CPC) is applicable in

³⁹ Upcounsel, History of Trademarks: Everything You Need to Know, <https://www.upcounsel.com/history-of-trademarks> (accessed on October 30, 2022).

⁴⁰ Institute of Intellectual Property, Chapter 2. The history and development of trademark law, <https://www.iip.or.jp/e/translation/pdf/ono/ch2.pdf> (accessed on October 30, 2022).

⁴¹ Upcounsel, Supra 39.

⁴² Id.

the European Economic Area. The consumers' authorities of Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein are therefore authorities of the CPC Network. The International Consumer Protection and Enforcement Network is a worldwide organization involving more than 40 countries, most of which are members of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The aim of the Network is to share information about cross-border commercial activities that may affect consumer interests, and to encourage international cooperation among law enforcement agencies. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development addresses a wide range of issues relevant to consumers.⁴³

The United Nations Guidelines for Consumer Protection, that were adopted in 1985 and revised in 1999, propose a list of objectives described as "legitimate needs": right to be heard; right to information; right to safety; right to choose; right to consumer education; promotion of economic interests of consumers. Many of these objectives appear to have their origins in human rights such as the right to safety for instance, which echoes the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The Southern African Development Community (SADC) is a Regional Economic Community comprising 15 Member States: Angola, Botswana, Democratic Republic of Congo, Lesotho, Madagascar, Malawi, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Seychelles, South Africa, Swaziland, Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe. Established in 1992, SADC is committed to Regional Integration and poverty eradication within Southern Africa through economic development and ensuring peace and security. The SADC set particular challenges for the consumers and, similarly to other regions in Africa, the increased liberalization of exchanges and the opening of trade borders put the SADC markets under particular stress. The SADC region has another challenger; that of limited access to justice, which makes it long, difficult, costly and sometimes just plain impossible for consumers to exercise their rights in case of abuse.⁴⁴

Ralph Nader, a leading American political activist and author is known as the father of the consumer movement.⁴⁵ Every society in history, where barter trade existed, has sought to

⁴³ Global Lex, Antonella Corradi, International Law and Consumer Protection: The history of consumer protection, https://www.nyulawglobal.org/globalex/International_Law_Consumer_Protection.html#_edn1 (accessed on October 30, 2022).

⁴⁴ Id.

⁴⁵ Byju's, Who Is Known as the Father of the Consumer Movement? <https://byjus.com/question-answer/who-is-known-as-the-father-of-the-consumer-movement/> (accessed on October 30, 2022).

develop a legal framework to define the relationship between the vendor and the buyer. As a result, elements of consumer (buyer) protection have appeared in public and/or private standards for centuries. Even under Roman law we find provisions to protect the buyer who entered into a contract, such as the right to claim defective goods.⁴⁶

Nepalese society has unknowingly developed the forms of IP and when Juddha Shamsher established Nepal Industrial Board along with other commercial factories and related laws to fulfill the development, he also introduced the law related to IP and named it Nepal Patent Design and Trademark Act 1993 BS which was replaced by Patent, Design and Trademark Act, 2022.

2.4 Functions of Trademark

A trademark serves the purpose of identifying the source or the origin of goods. Trademark performs the following four functions.⁴⁷

- a) It identifies the goods and services and its origin.
- b) It guarantees its unchanged quality.
- c) It advertises the goods and services.
- d) It creates an image for goods and services.

2.5 Types of trademark

Types of trademarks can be separated into general and specific types of trademarks.⁴⁸

2.5.1 General Types of Trademarks

What many professionals don't realize is that there are several different types of trademarks. These four categories also determine how strong the protection of a mark is. From top to bottom, these go from the weakest to the strongest. Understanding how each

⁴⁶ Česká Obchodní Inspekce, History of Consumer Protection Rights, <https://www.coi.cz/en/about-ctia/history-of-consumer-rights-protection/> (accessed on October 30, 2022).

⁴⁷ Advocate Khoj, Trademark, <https://www.advocatekhoj.com/library/lawareas/trade/functions.php?Title=Trademark&STitle=Functions%20of%20a%20Trademark>, (accessed on October 30, 2022).

⁴⁸ Types Of Trademarks: All You Need To Know, Abdulrahman Abou Naja, <https://www.mondaq.com/trademark/979316/types-of-trademarks-all-you-need-to-know> (accessed on October 11, 2022).

of these trademarks are or aren't protected could help establish long-running intellectual property protection of business.⁴⁹

a. Generic Mark

Generic marks represent the everyday descriptions of a product or its seller.⁵⁰ The weakest level of protection is provided to generic marks. In fact, these often don't get any protection at all and will be declined by the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO). Generic terms won't earn trademark protection as this would cause too much confusion over common terms and allows companies to monopolize language.⁵¹

b. Suggestive Mark

These trademarks are similar to descriptive trademarks, but they don't require secondary meaning because they describe something about the product in an indirect way.⁵² suggestive Marks register words that imply qualities of a product without necessarily relating to it in a literal sense. Imagination from the consumer's end is a primary consideration in classifying a mark as suggestive. A good example would be Netflix, as it alludes to its line of service without directly stating that it is an online streaming platform.⁵³

c. Descriptive Mark

While the generic mark may represent a product or its provider, a Descriptive Mark applies solely to the merchandise.⁵⁴ Descriptive trademarks are terms that describe the company or product it represents, but they must have at least one secondary meaning beyond simply just describing the product.⁵⁵

d. Arbitrary Mark and Fanciful Mark

The strongest protection for trademarks comes when there is no related meaning or description for the mark. In this case, the term will either be completely made up (fanciful)

⁴⁹THE FOUR TYPES OF TRADEMARKS, Alvarez Law Group, August 9, 2022, <https://alvarez.legal/the-four-types-of-trademarks/>, (accessed on October 11, 2022).

⁵⁰ Naja, Supra 48.

⁵¹Alvarez, Supra 49.

⁵² Id.

⁵³ Naja, Supra 48.

⁵⁴ Id.

⁵⁵ Alvarez, Supra 49.

or will be a common word or phrase that has no association with the actual product or company (arbitrary).⁵⁶ “Google” is an example of a made-up word that is considered fanciful while “Apple” is an example of an arbitrary mark as it has no direct connection to the technologies created by the tech giant.⁵⁷

2.5.2 Specific Types of Trademarks

These specific types of trademark are for the companies that provide service.⁵⁸

- a. Service Mark: A service mark is the same as a trademark, but it distinguishes a company that provides services instead of products.⁵⁹
- b. Certification Mark: This mark is registered to ascertain adherence to local regulations. Contrary to the other types of trademarks, a Certification Mark is used by an authorized user, not the owner.⁶⁰
- c. Collective Mark: Collective Marks are special trademarks owned by organizations or associations. This mark appears to distinguish organizational origin.⁶¹
- d. Trade Dress: A trade dress includes identifying features of a product or company such as packaging elements, décor items, and other similar concepts.⁶²
- e. Trade Name: Trade Names are used in identifying a company as a whole, instead of distinguishing a specific service or product. Proctor & Gamble is an excellent example of a trade name holding many trademarks such as Oral-B.⁶³
- f. House Mark: Similar to the trade name, a house mark identifies the manufacturing company or corporation. However, the difference is that House Marks are placed alongside the specific product names to identify it as belonging to the company.⁶⁴
- g. Family of Marks: The Family of Marks acts the same way as the house marks. However, the main difference lies in its form. It does not necessarily call for a full

⁵⁶ Id.

⁵⁷ Id.

⁵⁸Upcounsel, Types of Trademarks: Everything You Need to Know, June 26, 2020, <https://www.upcounsel.com/types-of-trademarks>, (accessed on October 11, 2022).

⁵⁹ Id.

⁶⁰ Naja, Supra 49.

⁶¹ Id.

⁶² Upcounsel, Supra 58

⁶³ Naja, Supra 49.

⁶⁴ Id.

name but makes use of abbreviations and initials. For eg; 'i' of apple in iPad, iPhone.⁶⁵

- h. Sound Mark: Commonly known as a "jingle", a Sound Mark is a unique sound or melody that has proven recognition for the brand. McDonald's had their sound mark registered for the infuriatingly catchy sound playing in each of their TV commercials.⁶⁶
- i. Pattern Mark: This type of mark, commonly found in the fashion industry, protects the specific way design is tiled into a canvass. Imagine Louis Vuitton and its famous pattern.⁶⁷
- j. Position Mark: Position Mark identifies the exact positioning of a mark with respect to its surrounding elements. For instance, logos appearing on shoes are placed using the same proportions across the line of footwear. However, the positioning itself must be considered unique to the company.⁶⁸
- k. Hologram Mark: With more advanced visual communication techniques, presenting a company logo may take contemporary forms. Hologram marks cover the three-dimensional picture shown in a holographic device.⁶⁹
- l. Multimedia Mark: Multimedia marks are perhaps most commonly seen in film production houses and the television industry. It contains a visual sequence with accompanying sound elements.
- m. Motion Mark: Although closely related to the multimedia mark, motion marks are purely visual in nature. It may be an animated logo that plays either on loop or as a one-time clip.⁷⁰
- n. Logotype: Logotypes encompass all logos that involve text or letters, whether the company's name, initials (monograms), or sometimes a person's signature. A

⁶⁵ Id.

⁶⁶ Id.

⁶⁷ Id.

⁶⁸ Id.

⁶⁹ Id.

⁷⁰ Id.

logotype tends to promote name recognition, and is associated with more traditional and formal approaches to branding.⁷¹

⁷¹99 designs for vista, Logotype vs. logomark vs. logo: What is the difference?, <https://99designs.com/blog/logo-branding/logotype-vs-logomark-vs-logo/> (accessed on November 12, 2022).

CHAPTER - III

INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL LEGAL PROVISIONS

3.1 International Legal Instruments

3.1.1 Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, 1883

Under the Paris Convention, each member state must grant similar protection to nationals of other member countries that it grants to its own nationals. Article 6b of the Paris Convention seeks its member countries to refuse or cancel the trademark registration, and to prohibit the use of a trademark which constitutes a reproduction, an imitation or a translation, liable to create confusion, of a mark considered by the competent authority of the country of registration or use to be well known in that country as being already the mark of a person entitled to the benefits of this Convention and used for identical or similar goods. The article 6b allows at least five years' timeframe to request the cancellation of such a mark from the date of registration.

3.1.1.1 Basic Principles

The provisions of the Paris Convention can be subdivided into four main categories:

Firstly, the rules of substantive law which guarantee in each Member State a fundamental right known as the right to national treatment,

Secondly, a basic right is known as a right of priority;

A 3rd category shall describe a number of common rules in the field of substantive law which shall include either rules establishing natural and legal persons' rights and obligations or rules requiring the Member States to legislate or permit them to enact legislation pursuant to those rules;

The fourth category encompasses the institutional structure for the application of the Convention and includes the Convention's final clauses.⁷²

3.1.2 Agreement On the Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, 1994

TRIPS came into effect on January 1995 as a multilateral agreement between WTO countries. Its major objective is to provide strong and comprehensive protection for various

⁷² Legal Bites, Ankita Mohanty, Major International Instruments | Intellectual Property, <https://www.legalbites.in/major-international-instruments-intellectual-property/>, 2020, (accessed on July 12, 2021).

forms of IP throughout the world. It lays down certain minimum standards for national governments for the regulation of copyright, trademarks, geographical indications, industrial designs, patents including the protection of new varieties of plants, layout designs of integrated circuits and undisclosed information including trade secrets and test data. The agreement requires compliance of the most recent amended version of WIPO, Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property and the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (Berne Convention). The TRIPS principally mandates member countries to formulate domestic IPR enforcement procedures to allow right holders to exercise their IPR rights and remedies for the contravention of the agreement. Under the TRIPS, disputes are subject to the WTO's dispute settlement procedure. The agreement requires developed countries to provide incentive to their enterprises to facilitate transfer of technology and forge technical and financial cooperation with LDCs to enable them to implement the agreement. The article 27.3 (b) of the TRIPS agreement enables the patentability of seeds and plants other than non-biological and micro-biological processes. The provision is contentious as it may lead to appropriation of indigenous knowledge and resources.

3.1.2.1 Basic Principles

The basic principle with regard to the nature and scope of TRIPS obligations is that the members should apply the provisions of the Agreement and grant the nationals of other members the treatment provided for in the agreement. A 'national' means natural or legal persons eligible for protection where all the World Trade Organization's members were also bound by the Paris, Berne and Rome conventions and, in relation to the Integrated Circuits, by the Washington Treaty on Intellectual Property.⁷³

The TRIPS Agreement includes the principle of the most favored nation that has not traditionally been established in the context of multilateral intellectual property rights. This principle stipulates that the nationality of all other Members, with certain specified exceptions, shall be granted immediately and unconditionally, to any advantage, privilege, or immunity granted by the Member to the nationals of any other country (whether or not a Member).

⁷³ Id.

3.1.3 Authority to inspect the violation of IPR

Crime does not occur in vacuum, so when it does there is the need to control and minimize those activities. In case of theft/ piracy of the intellectual properties, WIPO is the authority which provides aid to the countries in order to minimize them.

3.1.3.1 WIPO

The World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) is the global forum for intellectual property (IP) policy, services, information and cooperation.⁷⁴ A specialized agency of the United Nations, WIPO assists its 193 member states⁷⁵ in developing a balanced international IP legal framework to meet society's evolving needs.⁷⁶ It provides business services for obtaining IP rights in multiple countries and resolving disputes. It delivers capacity-building programs to help developing countries benefit from using IP.⁷⁷ And it provides free access to unique knowledge banks of IP information.⁷⁸

The list of service by WIPO are listed below:

- a. It provides a policy forum to shape balanced international IP rules for a changing world.
- b. Renders global services to protect IP across borders and to resolve disputes;
- c. Helps in technical infrastructure to connect IP systems and share knowledge;
- d. Establishes cooperation and capacity-building programs to enable all countries to use IP for economic, social and cultural development;
- e. It is a world reference source for IP information.

3.2 National Legal Instruments

In Nepal, the protection and enforcement of TM is primarily the Patent, Design and Trademark Act, 2022 (1965). In addition, Nepal is also a signatory to various intellectual property treaties such as the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property,

⁷⁴ WIPO, LinkedIn, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/wipo/> (accessed on October 19, 2022).

⁷⁵ WIPO, United States of America Joins WIPO's Marrakesh Treaty as 50th Member In Major Advance for the Global Blind Community, https://www.wipo.int/pressroom/en/articles/2019/article_0002.html, (accessed on October 19, 2022).

⁷⁶ WIPO, Supra 74.

⁷⁷ Global Innovation Index's Global Science & Technology Clusters: East Asia Dominates Top Ranking, https://www.wipo.int/pressroom/en/articles/2022/article_0010.html, (accessed on October 19, 2022).

⁷⁸ World Intellectual Property Day 2019 "Reach for Gold: IP and Sports", https://www.wipo.int/pressroom/en/articles/2019/article_0006.html, (accessed on October 19, 2022).

1883, the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, pursuant to which Nepal is under an obligation to safeguard TM. Nepal is also a member country of World Intellectual Property Organization.

3.2.1 Constitution of Nepal, 2072

20. Rights relating to justice: Every person shall have the right to a fair trial by an independent, impartial and competent court or judicial body.⁷⁹

25. Right relating to property: Every citizen shall, subject to law, have the right to acquire, own, sell, dispose, acquire business profits from, and otherwise deal with, property.⁸⁰

28. Right to privacy: Except in circumstances provided by law, privacy in relation to the person, and their residence, property, documents, records, statistics and correspondence, and their reputation are inviolable.⁸¹

3.2.2 Patent, Design and Trademark Act, 2022

According to the Patent, Design and Trademark Act, 2022, the department of industry shall register the trademark in the name of the applicant based on necessary examination of a trademark application. The department shall conduct necessary investigation and provide sufficient opportunity to the applicant to defend his/her case and also conduct further inquiry before registering it. The refusal of trademark application is based on following, if the applied trademark hurts the prestige of any individual or institution affects the public conduct or morality or undermine the national interest affects the reputation of the trademark of any other person is already registered in the name of another person The registered trademark will remain valid for seven years from the year of registration and can be renewed every seven years for any number of times.

(2) No one shall copy or use or cause to use in the name of the others without transforming the ownership or written permission pursuant to Section 21D, the patent registered in the name of any person pursuant to this Act.⁸² The Section 21D includes Transfer of ownership or approval for use of Patent, Design or Trade.⁸³

⁷⁹ Constitution of Nepal, Article 20, (2072).

⁸⁰ Constitution of Nepal, Article 25, (2072).

⁸¹ Constitution of Nepal, Article 28, (2072).

⁸² Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 3(2), (2022).

⁸³ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 21(D), (2022).

11. Penalty for violation of Section 3

(a) A fine of up to Five Hundred Thousand Rupees for use or cause to use in the name of the others without transforming the ownership or written permission.

(b) A fine of up to Two Hundred and Fifty Thousand (Two lac fifty thousand) Rupees for committing an attempt or abetment of an offense mentioned above.⁸⁴

18B. Prohibition to Use Trademarks: No trade-mark may be used as a registered trade-mark without registering it at the Department.⁸⁵

18C. Time Limit for Use of Trademarks: In case a trade-mark registered at the Department is not brought into use within one year from the date of registration thereof, the department shall conduct necessary inquiries and cancel such registration.⁸⁶

19. Punishment for illegal use of trade-marks

In case anyone who copies or uses or causes to use in the name of the others without transforming the ownership or written permission or brings into use a trademark which has been cancelled or uses unregistered trademarks may be punished with a fine not exceeding is One Hundred Thousand Rupees and articles and goods connected with such offense confiscated on the orders of the Department as per the gravity of offense.⁸⁷

25. Compensation: In case a person whose patent, design or trademark has been registered under this Act, suffers any losses as a result of violation of the provisions of this Act by any others person in respect to the patent, design or trade-mark, the Department may order to amount actually by the title holder from such offender in the form of compensation.⁸⁸

3.2.3 Consumer Protection Act, 2075

Product which is different or pirated or imitated from the product produced by the manufacturing company possessing the intellectual property right are considered as defective products. Hence, such defective products shall not be provided to the consumers.⁸⁹

⁸⁴ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 11, (2022).

⁸⁵ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 18(B), (2022).

⁸⁶ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 18(C), (2022).

⁸⁷ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 19, (2022).

⁸⁸ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 25, (2022).

⁸⁹ Consumer Protection Act, Section 2(R) (5), (2075).

The section 3 of the act provides for the rights of the consumers⁹⁰ which includes things like right to choose quality goods or services at the fair competitive price,⁹¹ right to be informed of the price, quantity, purity, quality etc. of the goods or services,⁹² right to be safe from the sale and distribution of the goods and services that inflict harm to the human body, life, health and property,⁹³ right to get appropriate legal action taken against the unfair trade and business activities,⁹⁴ right to obtain compensation against harm and injury caused with the use of goods or services,⁹⁵ right to get consumer education⁹⁶ etc.

According to the act, Government of Nepal shall regulate the supplies, price, quality, measurement, label, advertisement of the goods and services regularly in order to protect the rights of the consumers.⁹⁷

3.2.4 National Intellectual Property Policy, 2017

The National Intellectual Property Policy, 2017 incorporates wide issues relating to IP with a view to develop balanced IP management system in Nepal. The policy seeks to: develop new legal framework or revise the existing ones for copyright, patent, industrial design, trademark, geographical indication, plant species, trade secrets, integrated circuit, layout design, traditional and indigenous knowledge, traditional cultural expression and folklore, biodiversity and genetic resource in line with the country's needs use existing traditional knowledge, biodiversity and geographical indication as a tool for national development use IP as a source for environment-friendly technology transfer, foreign investment, research promotion and development of technical capacity and knowledge increase awareness about IP and its importance for the economic, social and cultural progress of the society encourage commercialization of all forms of IP Develop strong laws and institutional and human resources to enforce protection of IPR Develop a separate institutional mechanism namely National Intellectual Property Council to enforce effective execution of policies set out in the National Intellectual Property Policy, 2017 Develop a separate and integrated IP Office under DoI to look after the promotion, protection and recording of IPR.

⁹⁰ Consumer Protection Act, Section 3, (2075).

⁹¹ Consumer Protection Act, Section 3 (b), (2075).

⁹² Consumer Protection Act, Section 3 (c), (2075).

⁹³ Consumer Protection Act, Section 3 (e), (2075).

⁹⁴ Consumer Protection Act, Section 3 (f), (2075).

⁹⁵ Consumer Protection Act, Section 3 (g), (2075).

⁹⁶ Consumer Protection Act, Section 3 (i), (2075).

⁹⁷ Consumer Protection Act, Section 4, (2075).

3.2.5 Authorities to inspect the violation of IPR

Under the existing IPR regime, the Ministry of Industry, Commerce, & Supplies' Department of Industry looks after patent and trademark issues while the Ministry of Culture, Tourism, and Civil Aviation oversees copyright issues.

Nepal has a consolidated Act on IP – The Patent, Design and Trademark Act that provides protection for industrial property including patents, designs, and trademarks. Patent protection is afforded to inventions; principles and formulae; design protection including physical shape and appearance. Trademark protections include the word, sign, picture, or combination thereof to differentiate the product from others in the market.

Courts generally have the appellate jurisdiction to the cases relating to IP. The following other authorities have the original jurisdiction in their specialized sectors.

The Department of Industry(DoI) acts as a semi-judiciary unit in cases of protection of industrial property as well as in the settlement of disputes and other administrative procedures.⁹⁸ It is one of the major agencies at ministry of industry, responsible for implementation of policies and acts related to industrial development.

Nepal Standard and Quality Office relating to National Standard Mark. It provides a National Standard Mark and each product bearing such mark shall have met the requirements of the standard applicable the such product ensuring quality and safety of them.

Post Offices:

- If upon investigation, any restricted news, articles, books or if found out that the found materials are written by someone else then the post office can seize such documents.⁹⁹

Police Departments: Nepal Police is the main law enforcement agency of the country which is primarily responsible for enforcement and maintenance of existing laws among people.

- The police shall make necessary arrangements for preventing the copies of work, sound recording or other materials from being sold and distributed and may, in cases

⁹⁸ International Trade Administration, Protecting Intellectual Property, <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/nepal-protecting-intellectual-property> 2020, (accessed on July 11, 2021).

⁹⁹ Postal Act, Section 22, (2019).

where required, search the copies of such work or sound recording and seize the same pursuant to the law in force.¹⁰⁰

- The cases of copyright violation shall be the state case.¹⁰¹
- A police officer of at least the rank of police inspector shall investigate and inquire into the cases under this Act to the cases punishable under Sections 27 and 28.
- Pillar number 5 of Metropolitan Police crime division is dedicated for ICT crimes and IPR infringement cases.

Nodal Officer

Nodal officer is a job title within the police department (focal person), also known as complaint handling officer (regarding issues of IP).

3.3 Cases relating to Trademark Infringement

3.3.1 Cadbury India Limited and Ors. V. Neeraj Food Products

In the case of Cadbury India Limited and Ors. V. Neeraj Food Products¹⁰², the High Court of Delhi explained the difference between passing off action and an action for trade mark infringement as under: An action for trade mark infringement is a statutory remedy and on the other hand, an action for passing off is a common law remedy. The use of the trade mark of the plaintiff, by the defendant, is also a prerequisite in the case of an action for infringement while it is not a necessity of an action for passing off. In an action for infringement of the plaintiff's trade mark, it is immaterial that the outfit, outer covering and other written marks on the goods originate from a different source than that of a registered proprietor's trade mark. The liability of the defendant in such a case may be absolute. However, in case of passing off of trade mark, the defendant may escape liability if he can show that the material added by him is sufficient to distinguish his goods from that of the plaintiff's goods. In an action for infringement, the Plaintiff on account of it being a registered trade mark in dispute claims to have an exclusive right to use the mark concerning those goods. However, a passing off by a person of his goods as those of another, in essence, is an action of deceit.¹⁰³

¹⁰⁰ Copyright Act, Section 32, (2059).

¹⁰¹ Copyright Act, Section 37, (2059).

¹⁰² Cadbury India Limited and Ors. V. Neeraj Food Products, AIR, (HC 2007).

¹⁰³ Khurana & Khurana Advocates and IP Attorneys, India: Difference Between Passing Off And Infringement Of The Trade Mark, , <https://www.mondaq.com/india/trademark/902156/difference-between-passing-off-and-infringement-of-the-trade-mark> (accessed on November 10, 2022).

3.3.2 Sandeep Industries V. Sun Fitting Pvt. Ltd D. No. 10304.

In Sandeep Industries V. Sun Fitting Pvt. Ltd it was concluded that, apart from giving a distinct identity to the goods produced by the company or entrepreneur, the trademark also helps to maintain the source and quality of the goods and to distinguish them from other businesses or brands that produce similar goods. Since trademark words, pictures or logos, designs or other identifying features are used to distinguish different goods in the market, basically the purpose of trademark registration is to identify the goods or goods in an introductory manner to the general public and to remove the negative confusion that may be caused by maintaining the quality of the goods or goods, in the market. It is to maintain fair competition and protect the commercial reputation of the owner of the trademark. If a trademark used by someone else is used in an unauthorized manner in such a way as to create confusion or mislead, the owner of the trademark will have the right to prevent such action.¹⁰⁴

3.3.3 Louis Vuitton Malletier S.A. v. Haute Diggity Dog, LLC. - 507 F.3d 252 (4th Cir. 2007)

In 2007, the high-end signature hand-bag and luggage maker, Louis Vuitton Malletier, lost an outrageous copyright infringement case against comedy fashion company Haute Diggity Dog. The comedy designers had released a line of parody products named Chewy Vuitton, to go along with other memorable knock-offs such as Chewnel No.5 and Sniffany & Co. Remarkably, the U.S Court of Appeals ruled against the claim of copyright breach, stating that because of the element of parody, the products were adequately differentiated and unique, thereby negating any copyright or trademark infringement.¹⁰⁵

3.3.4 Tejram Dharampal VS Gadapati Tobacco¹⁰⁶ the Petitioner's mark had been published in the IP Bulletin for Opposition, which was then opposed by the Respondent on the grounds of 'first to file' rule. The DoI refused the opposition and decided in favor of the Petitioner. The Respondent then, appealed before the High Court of Patan against the decision of DoI. The High Court quashed the decision given by DoI and issued order to the DoI instructing to register the trademark in the name of the Respondent. Thereafter, the

¹⁰⁴ Sandeep Industries V. Sun Fitting Pvt. Ltd, NKP, (SC 2075).

¹⁰⁵ Louis Vuitton Malletier S.A. v. Haute Diggity Dog, F.Supp.3d, 252, (Forth Circuit, 2007).

¹⁰⁶ Tejram Dharampal VS Gadapati Tobacco, NLR, (SC, 2076).

Petitioner filed a petition with the Supreme Court requesting to quash the decision made by the High Court, Patan.

The petitioner contended that they were the lawful proprietor and the prior user of the "RAJ NIWAS" mark and the mark is well known in the Indian and Nepali market and it had obtained protection through the registration of the mark in Lebanon and UAE. The Respondent in its written response contended that it was the first to apply for registration in Nepal, it had invested huge amount for its promotion and development and had paid more than 2 crores as tax to the Inland Revenue Department. The Respondent also stated that the Petitioner had failed to provide proof of their Home Registration at the time of registration in Nepal.

Regarding well-known marks and the protection granted under Article 6b of the Paris Convention, the court emphasized on the provision of the Convention whereby it provides that the conditions for the filing and registration of the trademarks shall be determined in each country of the Union by its domestic legislation which means that the applicant must fulfil all the legal formalities for the registration of a mark in Nepal. The Petitioner had applied for the registration of the mark on the basis of its home registration; however, the mark had not been registered in the home country itself at the time of filing the application. Trademark application and trademark registration are two different things. The PDTA clearly states that the trademark must be registered in the foreign country of origin in case of a foreign mark application in Nepal.¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁷ Pioneer Law Associates, IP Case Precedents, <http://www.pioneerlaw.com/news/ip-case-precedents> (accessed on August 16, 2021).

CHAPTER - IV

DATA PRESENTATION

The researcher collected total of 116 responses, [*101 online responses and 15 field responses*]. The data below is the result of the survey and contains raw responses.

Some of the preliminary section's questions [Name, Email....] have been skipped to maintain confidentiality of the respondents.

4.1 Gender and Age of respondents

A total of 116 responses were collected on question relating to gender and age of the respondents. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 1 Gender and Age of respondents

Age	Responses and Gender	Percentage
18-28	53 Male, 54 Female	45.69% Male, 46.54% Female
29-38	4 Male	3.44% Male
48+	4 Male, 1 Female	3.44% Male, 0.86% Female
Total	116	100%

The survey included question of gender and age in the preliminary section. Total of 116 responses were collected out of which 53 males and 54 Females from age group 18-28, 4 males from age group 29-38, 4 males and a female from age group 48+ filled the above mentioned question of survey questionnaire.

Graph 1 Gender and Age of respondents

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.2 Preference of Brands

A total of 116 responses were collected on question relating to brand preference while purchasing of the respondents. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 2 Preference of Brands

Preference of Brand	Responses	Percentage
Yes	40	34.48%
No	9	7.76%
Depends on the situation and need	66	56.89%
Total	116	100%

The survey included question of brand preference while making a purchase. Total of 116 responses were collected out of which 40 respondents said Yes, 9 said No and 66 said that it depends on the situation and need in the above mentioned question of survey questionnaire.

Graph 2 Preference of Brands

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.3 Information regarding purchase

A total of 115 responses were collected on question relating to respondent's habit of getting information regarding their purchase. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 3 Information regarding purchase

Information regarding purchase	Responses	Percentage
Always	23	20%
Depends on the product	60	52.17%
Often	28	24.34%
Never	3	2.61%
Total	115	100%

The survey included question of whether the respondents try to get information regarding their purchase or not. Total of 115 responses were collected out of which 23 said always, 60 said it depends on the product, 28 said often and 3 said never.

Graph 3 Information regarding purchase

INFORMATION ABOUT PRODUCTS PURCHASED FOR CONSUMPTION

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.4 Ability to distinguish the real and fake products

A total of 116 responses were collected on question relating to respondents' ability to distinguish real and fake products. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 4 Ability to distinguish the real and fake products

Ability to distinguish real and fake products	Responses	Percentage
Yes	20	17.24%
Yes, but not all products	83	71.55%
No	12	10.34%
Total	116	100%

The survey included question if the respondents can distinguish between real and fake product or not. Total of 116 responses were collected out of which 20 said yes, 83 said yes, but not all products and 12 said no.

Graph 4 Ability to distinguish the real and fake products

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.5 Purchased duplicate product thinking it is real.

A total of 116 responses were collected on question relating to respondents' ability to distinguish real and fake products. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 5 Purchased duplicate product thinking it is real.

Purchased duplicate product thinking it is real.	Responses	Percentage
A lot of times	27	23.3%
Sometimes	64	55.2 %
Never	25	21.5%
Total	116	100%

The survey included question if the respondents made a purchase of a fake product thinking it is real. Total of 116 responses were collected out of which 27 said a lot of times, 64 said sometimes, and 25 said never.

Graph 5 Purchased duplicate product thinking it is real.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.6 Sectors of Confusion

A total of 115 responses were collected on question relating to respondents' sectors of confusion regarding trademark. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 6 Sectors of Confusion.

Sectors of Confusion	Responses	Percentage
Food	39	33.91%
Clothes and Shoes	68	59.13%
Medicine	21	18.26%
Beauty Products	2	1.74%
Electronics	1	0.869%
Others	2	1.74%
Nowhere	1	0.869%

The survey included question if the respondents made a purchase of a fake product thinking it is real. Total of 115 responses were collected out of which 39 said Food, 68 said Clothes and Shoes, 21 said Medicine, 2 said beauty product, 1 said electronics, 2 said others and 1 said nowhere.

Graph 6 Sectors of Confusion.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.7 Complains regarding duplicate products

A total of 82 responses were collected on question regarding complaints by respondents about duplicate products. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 7 Complains regarding duplicate products.

Complains regarding duplicate products	Responses	Percentage
Shopkeeper	57	69.21%
Main Supplier	14	17.07%
Internet Consumer Forum	5	6.097%
Did not complain	5	6.097%
Elsewhere	1	1.22%1.
Total	82	100%

The survey included question if the respondents made a complaint of a fake product. Total of 82 responses were collected out of which 57 said they complained with shopkeeper, 14 said they complained with main supplier 5 complained Internet Consumer Forum 5 did not complain, and 1 of them complained elsewhere.

Graph 7 Complains regarding duplicate products.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.8 Did not take action regarding fake product.

A total of 80 responses were collected on why did the respondents did not take action regarding the fake product they purchased. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 8 Did not take action regarding fake product.

Did not take action regarding fake product.	Responses	Percentage
Unknown about law	27	33.75%
Did not feel the need	24	30%
Procedural Hassle	27	33.75%
Complain Depends on situation and products	1	1.25%
Voice will not be heard	1	1.25%
Total	80	100%

The survey included question if the respondents why did the respondents not complain about the fake products. Total of 80 responses were collected out of which 27 said they were unknown about law, 24 said they did not feel the need, 27 said procedural hassle, 1

said complain depends on situation and products and 1 said that the voice raised will not be raised.

Graph 8 Did not take action regarding fake product.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.9 Awareness regarding laws.

A total of 114 responses were collected on question relating to respondents' ability to distinguish real and fake products. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 9 Awareness regarding laws.

Awareness regarding law	Responses	Percentage
Yes	30	26.32%
Yes, but not in detail	49	42.98%
No	35	30.70%
Total	114	100%

The survey included question if the respondents are aware of existing laws. Total of 114 responses were collected out of which 30 said yes, 49 said yes, but not in detail, and 35 said no.

Graph 9 Awareness regarding laws.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.10 Assurance as a business person

A total of 113 responses were collected on if the respondents feel safe as a business person in the Nepalese market. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 10 Assurance as a business person.

Assurance as a business person	Responses	Percentage
Safe	10	8.85%
Pretty Safe	21	18.58%
Not safe at all	62	54.87%
It is not safe in any part of the world, safety of TM is on self	20	17.699%
Total	113	100%

The survey included question if the respondents feel safe as a business person in the Nepalese market. Total of 113 responses were collected out of which 10 said safe, 21 said pretty safe, 62 said not safe at all and 20 said it is not safe in any part of the world, safety of TM is on self never.

Graph 10 Assurance as a business person.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.11 Possibility of copying trademark.

A total of 111 responses were collected on if there is possibility of copying trademark in the Nepalese market. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 11 Possibility of copying trademark.

Possibility of copying trademark	Responses	Percentage
Yes, but would not do so because we believe we will be punished	42	37.8%
Yes, Nepalese law is easy to get away with	40	36%
No, neither me or people I know cannot do that.	29	26.1%
Total	111	100%

The survey included question if the respondents about the possibility of trademarks being copied in the Nepalese market. Total of 111 responses were collected out of which 42 said yes, but would not do so because we believe we will be punished, 40 said yes, Nepalese law is easy to get away with, 29 said no, neither me or people I know cannot do that.

Graph 11 Possibility of copying trademark.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.12 Effectiveness of Trademark related laws in Nepal.

A total of 114 responses were collected on question relating to effectiveness of trademark related laws in Nepal. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 12 Effectiveness of Trademark related laws in Nepal.

Effectiveness of Trademark related laws in Nepal	Responses	Percentage
Excellent	1	0.877%
Good	13	11.40%
Average	52	45.61%
Poor	49	42.98%
Total	114	100%

The survey included question if the respondents about the effectiveness of TM related laws in the Nepalese market. Total of 114 responses were collected out of which 1 said excellent, 13 said good, 52 said average and 49 said poor.

Graph 12 Effectiveness of Trademark related laws in Nepal.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.13 Reasons behind lack of law enforcement.

A total of 113 responses were collected on reasons behind lack of law enforcement in Nepal. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 13 Reasons behind lack of law enforcement.

Reasons behind lack of law enforcement	Responses	Percentage
Poor implementation of laws by government	40	35.4%
Weakness of people for not using existing laws	30	26.5%
Irrational decisions of court	7	6.2%
All of the above	60	53.1%

The survey included question what can be reasons behind lack of law enforcement to the respondents. Total of 113 responses were collected out of which 40 said poor implementation of laws by government, 30 said weakness of people for not using existing laws, 7 said irrational decisions of courts and 60 said all of the above.

Graph 13 Reasons behind lack of law enforcement.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.14 Role of government for protection of such infringement.

A total of 113 responses were collected on role of government for protection of such infringement. The responses are tabulated and graphically presented below:

Table 14 Role of government for protection of such infringement.

Role of government for protection of such infringement	Responses	Percentage
Role of the government is very important but looks like it's just there for the formality, not satisfactory.	53	46.90%
Government's role is to make laws and there are enough laws related to the topic.	11	9.73%
Implementation of existing laws is also a part of role of government in this context.	48	42.48%
Insufficient Laws	3	2.65%

The survey included question regarding role of government for protection of TM infringement to the respondents. Total of 113 responses were collected out of which 53 said

role of the government is very important but looks like it's just there for the formality, not satisfactory, 11 said government's role is to make laws and there are enough laws related to the topic, 48 said implementation of existing laws is also a part of role of government in this context.

Graph 14 Role of government for protection of such infringement.

Source: Online and Field Survey.

4.15 Experiences

The responses regarding the experiences of the respondents related to the topic were collected. Only 18 responses have been recorded since the question was not a mandatory one. The responses are listed below:

1) No I haven't experience such because I am always careful and I observe each and every product carefully before buying it.

2) I buy kurkure, turns out its kurure.

3) No I can't remember much about the incidents because this type of incident happens on regular basis.

4) *I don't remember anything in particular, but there could have been such instances definitely especially when purchasing something in bulk.*

5) *I bought the Puma outerwear thinking it was branded one from one of the Newroad shop but later I found it was just a fake logo sticker attached to it.*

6) *Mostly in online stores, products are very different from the description and expenses.*

7) *It was about 5-6 years ago, my mom bought a shampoo at extremely lower price from some random street vendor and she didn't check the trademark correctly. It was "head & shampoo" instead of "head & shoulder". The next day she went to return the fake product, the shop wasn't there. Then we had to use it anyway, the product did no good at all. Also, recently whenever I go to shop to buy Red Bull, I haven't found the real one in quite a while.*

8) *Purchased a Nike shoe with a Nike logo at relatively high price. But later I found it was a fake product with fake branding.*

9) *Not much because to some extent shopkeepers are also unaware of the consequences.*

10) *I have bought fake makeup products. Similarly, I have purchased fake potato chips, soaps, pencils things like this. I didn't take any action due to not knowing laws but now I am aware about it and would definitely take necessary action if such things again happen with me.*

11) *Once I did online shopping from my fb ID, but the size of shoe is smaller than my size, when I call to complain about my size they replied that, sir, u can visit my store at some location as they said but when I went there the shop was closed. I feel cheated from them.*

12) *Most of the product we buy in Nepal are not genuine, we have been used to it so even if we are deceived we will ignore it, I ignore it cause fighting for social good comes with great loss of time and effort, still there won't be justice.*

13) *Shopkeepers don't feel brand is important. They sell duplicate product also because it's price relatively low. But when customer buy they product, they just lost and buy duplicate one and when they use it and they realize that was not real. In this way, unknowingly customer buy duplicated product and that was very worst. for example, duplicate of coke, duplicate of Nike, duplicate of beauty product. When we use duplicate product of beauty and that was never in good quality and we face variety of skin and face issue even that we can't complain about that because we know there very long procedure of government office, even that we are not sure that we will win and the fake producer will get punished. So that people don't want to complain about. And people face lot of problem from that duplicated product. I think making fair in every sector even food, clothes, beauty product, automobiles, every sector, that is duty of government.*

14) *I got duplicate laptop charger and battery.*

15) *So, once I went to buy a Nike Jordan that's very popular. I paid almost 11 thousand Nepalese rupees but alas it was a duplicate first copy. However, I couldn't complain to anyone because in Nepal I think fake products are imported and sold as an original one.*

16) I bought a smartphone which looks like original but later when I used it, I realized that it is completely fake.

17) Food alteration high. Comparing to foreign countries laws are not effective, especially in Kathmandu due to which consumers suffer a lot.

18) Bought and had "Red Blue" instead of "Red Bull", didn't necessarily complained about it but told the shopkeeper the next time I went to that shop. He said that's what we are supplied and can do nothing about it.

CHAPTER – V

DATA ANALYSIS.

A Survey on Trademark Infringement in Nepal Vis à vis Consumer Protection with total of 116 respondents was carried out by the researcher where 13.79% of the total responses were collected from field survey where as 86.21% of the responses were collected through online survey. Out of 116 responses collected 45.69% males and 46.54% Females from age group 18-28, 3.44% males from age group 29-38, 3.44% males and 0.86% female from age group 48+ filled the survey.

This is a descriptive and analytical study on trademark infringement and consumer protection. The majority of respondents in the survey conducted include the age group of 18-28 from various background such as law, medicine, business etc. Since, the data was collected through survey questionnaire, non-doctrinal approach has been adopted by the researcher. But the report is not solely based on the non-doctrinal data it also includes data from doctrinal sources.

The secondary data of this research were collected from different sources like published and unpublished reports, articles on the concerned subject, published documents of Department of Industry, statistics reports prepared by WIPO, various books written by scholars, newspaper articles and various websites.

The major objective of the survey was to find out if there exists trademark infringement in the markets of Nepal and that causes confusion to the general public aka consumers. The study covers the following questions were used to meet the objective of the researcher:

5.1 Buying habit/ Brand preference and Information regarding purchase.

Out of 116 respondents 34.48% of people said that the brand matters to them while making a purchase and 7.76% of people said that the brand does not matter to them where as 56.89% i.e. the majority of people said that buying branded item depends on the product and the situation and not always.

The 20% of the respondents said always, 52.17% i.e. said it depends on the product, 24.34% said often and 2.61% of the 115 respondents said that they never try to get information about the product they purchase.

So, according to the majority of people do not always purchase branded products and it really depends on the product and the situation of the respondents [if they have money] whether to prefer brand or not while buying the required product.

5.2 Ability to distinguish real and fake products. The 17.24% of the total 116 respondents said that they can distinguish between the real and the fake product, 71.55% of them said that they can make a distinction but not of all products and rest of the 10.34% said no.

Maybe, the consumers should be aware on their own as well in order to get quality products at their reasonable prices. Ignorance of information is no excuse?

Senior Advocate Jyoti Baniya says that Consumer rights protection in Nepal is the bare minimum with the market largely unregulated.¹⁰⁸ The sellers are also not being responsible for creating false and exaggerated advertisements that mislead the consumers to purchase the duplicate goods.¹⁰⁹

5.3 Purchased duplicate products thinking it is real.

Section 19 of the PDT Act, 2022 has a provision of punishment for illegal use of trademark.¹¹⁰ It has the provision of the offenders being punished with a fine not exceeding One Hundred Thousand Rupees and articles and goods connected with such offense confiscated on the orders of the Department as per the gravity of offense.

Consumer Protection Act, 2075 under Section 3 has the provision of rights of consumers¹¹¹ under which rights like right to get appropriate legal action taken against the unfair trade and business activities, right to obtain compensation against harm and injury caused with the use of goods or services etc. have been included.

Out of 116 respondents 23.3% of them said that they have made a purchase of a fake product thinking it is the real one and 55.2% of them responded that they made such purchase quite a few times and the 21.6% of them responded never.

The purchase of fake product thinking it is real can be due to the consumer's own carelessness or the degree of fakeness of product.

5.3.1 Sectors of Confusion.

¹⁰⁸ KII with Chairperson at Forum for Protection of Consumer Rights Nepal and Nepal Chairperson for SDG goal 12, Senior Advocate Jyoti Baniya, March 15, 2022. <https://english.onlinekhabar.com/consumer-rights-nepal-jyoti-baniya.html> (accessed on November 13, 2022).

¹⁰⁹ Id.

¹¹⁰ Patent, Design and Trademark Act, Section 19, (2022).

¹¹¹ Consumer Protection Act, Section 3, (2075).

The researcher upon the research found out that the majority of the confusion in the Nepalese market lie on the clothes and shoe i.e. 59.13% of the total 115 respondents responded that way and the confusion on food is 33.91%, confusion on medicine is 18.26%, confusion on beauty products is 1.74%, confusion on electronics is 0.869% and 1.74% responded others whereas 0.869% responded nowhere.

Even if the law prohibits existence of such infringed products that can confuse the consumers, in reality such products massively exist in the market which clarifies the situation of implementation of law in Nepal.

6 Complaints and No complaints regarding duplicate products.

The punishment for illegal use of trademark is fine not exceeding One Hundred Thousand Rupees and articles and goods connected with such offense confiscated on the orders of the Department as per the gravity of offense.¹¹² The Chapter 7 of the Consumer Protection Act, 2075 has a provision relating to inquiry, inspection and monitoring of the rights and interests of the consumers or for making coordination among the bodies involved in the monitoring or inspection of the supply system, price, quality and purity of the goods or services.¹¹³ There is also a provision relating to complaint¹¹⁴ in Section 36 and to ask for compensation¹¹⁵ in Section 50 of the Act.

After the purchase of the fake products thinking it is real 69.21% of the total 82 respondents complained about it to the shopkeeper, 17.07% to main supplier, 6.09% to the Internet consumer forum, 1.22% complained elsewhere and other 6.09% did not complain anywhere.

The 33.75% of the respondents who did not make any complaints about their purchase was because they were unknown about the law, 30% did not feel the need to complain 33.75% took it as a procedural hassle one of the 80 respondents i.e. 1.25% of them said that the complaint depends on the situation and products and the other 1.25% of them responded that the voices will not be heard even if they make a complain.

¹¹² Patent, Design, Trademark Act, Section 19, (2020).

¹¹³ Consumer Protection Act, Chapter 7, (2075).

¹¹⁴ Consumer Protection Act, Section 36, (2075).

¹¹⁵ Consumer Protection Act, Section 50,(2075).

Here, the 30% of the respondents who did not feel the need to complain might have felt so because of the amount money they spent on the fake product or because they also felt like the 1.25% of them; their voices going unheard. These responses reflect the status of public faith upon the law and the authorities.

Of the total violations, maybe just 2 per cent are reported. The reports are also reported by the organization and really by the individuals. I mean to say the legal provisions might be inefficient but the biggest problem is public ignorance. It's because when the violations are reported, the response from the authorities has been good.¹¹⁶

7 Awareness regarding laws and assurance as a business person.

The existing laws of Nepal are more than enough to provide a better market environment for consumers as well as business persons but as the majority of respondents have responded the problem lies in the implementation of the existing laws.

Regarding the knowledge and awareness of the laws in general public 26.32% of the total 114 respondents (majority of law students) said that they were aware of the law on concerned topic, 42.98% of the respondents said that they were aware of the laws but not in detail and the 30.7% of them said that they were not aware of the laws on trademark infringement and consumer protection.

The researcher had included a question regarding how assured do they feel as a business person in Nepal and out of 113 of them 8.85% of them said they feel it is safe, 18.58% said pretty safe, 54.87% of them said not safe at all and rest of the 17.699% said that it is not safe in any part of the world and the safety of your trademark really depends on self rather than country.

Ignorance of law is no excuse but still majority of the general public are unaware of the law, their fundamental and legal rights and duties which is a sad reality of our society. This ignorance of law can also be a major reason for disbelief of public towards law and authority.

8 Possibility of copying trademark.

¹¹⁶ Supra, Baniya 110.

Out of 111 respondents, 37.8% said yes, but would not do so because we believe we will be punished, 36% said yes, Nepalese law is easy to get away with, and 26.1% said no, neither me or people I know cannot do that.

Concluding from the data above, 73.8% of the total respondent responded that they or the people they know can easily copy the existing trademark existing in the markets. This data shows the threat to trademark if not protected and how easy it is to copy the trademark and create fake products. One of the KII also mentioned the fact that the complaints regarding trademark infringement is registered every day.¹¹⁷

9 Effectiveness of Trademark related laws in Nepal.

Out of the 114 respondents, 0.877% of the total respondents said that the effectiveness of TM related laws is excellent, 11.40% said that it is good, 45.61% said average, and 42.98% said that it is poor.

The responses of the data collected by the researcher shows that the effectiveness of the trademark related laws is very poor in Nepal which is also supported by the point number 4 of this Chapter. The confusion among the consumers on various items shows that the trademark infringed goods exist in the market enough to confuse people.

Consumer rights are violated in every aspect of the market. It is seen in terms of production and quality of the goods and services, valuation of the products, government's pro activeness or implementation of the law.¹¹⁸ Despite the law being on paper for more than two decades, its implementation in every form and manner has been to its bare minimum.¹¹⁹

The Law of trademark is very old one. It is of 2022 BS and it is 2022 AD now. It's high time the laws should be amended and add new provisions to keep up with the market. Many provisions such as passing off of trademark should be added.¹²⁰

Another reason why the laws of trademark is not effective in Nepal is because both the sellers and buyers are unaware of trademarks and its laws. The economic status of the majority of buyers in Nepal is not high enough to buy expensive and qualitative products which causes the flourishing of sales of duplicate products.¹²¹

¹¹⁷ KII with Mr Ramchandra Tiwari on September 21, 2022; Director General of Department of Industry.

¹¹⁸ Supra, Baniya, 110.

¹¹⁹ Id.

¹²⁰ KII with Law Adjunct Professor, Dr. Ram Babu Dhakal on October 22, 2022;

¹²¹ Id.

10 Reasons behind lack of law enforcement.

The respondents were allowed to choose multiple reasons on this question. Out of 113 respondents, 35.4% of them said that it was because of poor implementation of laws by government, 26.5% of them said that it is the weakness of people for not using existing laws, 6.2% of them said irrational decisions of court and 53.1% of them said all of the above opinions for poor enforcement of the existing laws in Nepal.

Senior Advocate Jyoti Baniya says that, “Sellers need to take the responsibility of providing quality products to the consumers.”¹²² But at the same time the government is also responsible for lack of law enforcement. According to the law, after the federal system is in effect, the local units are required to set up a local market as per the Subnational Governance Program. So far, only Bagmati Province passed the programme but it is yet to set up the market. Meanwhile, Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration (MoFAGA) have adopted the programme and working accordingly. Likewise, only 33 local-level municipalities have moved forward with the process so it will be a while before we see a regulated market and ensure the rights of the consumers as per the law.¹²³

The level of awareness of the concerned parties; the buyers, sellers affects the level of law enforcement. Only the people of business community are properly are of these laws. Professor Dr. Ram Babu Dhakal also focused on lack of laws along with its enforcement. The procedural hassle of the existing laws is also one of the major reasons for its poor enforcement. People have already suffered and if they have to again suffer while seeking for justice, they would rather give up.¹²⁴

11 Role of government for protection of such infringement.

¹²² Supra, Baniya, 110.

¹²³ Id.

¹²⁴Supra, Dhakal 122.

Provision of consumer court¹²⁵, Government to be plaintiff in cases under the act¹²⁶, Formation of Central Market Monitoring Committee¹²⁷ and other committees¹²⁸, to confiscate or destroy sub-standard goods¹²⁹ etc. On the question regarding role of the government for protection of such infringement, 46.9% of the 113 respondents said that the role of the government is very important but looks like it's just there for the formality, not satisfactory, 9.73% of them said that government's role is to make laws and there are enough laws related to the topic, 42.48% of them said that the implementation of existing laws is also a part of role of government in this context and the 2.65% said the laws are insufficient.

The government authorities are the least bit worried about what goes on in the market. The officials are politically inclined and feel that market monitoring and evaluation is not their priority. Meanwhile, the Department of Supply Management and Protection of Consumers does not even have the required human resources or the budget to conduct the monitoring.¹³⁰

Being the Director General of DoI, Mr. Ram Chandra Tiwari says that actions are being taken against the complaints filed in DoI. If people make a complaint then it will definitely be heard by the authority, hence, the government is playing active role in solving the issues raised.¹³¹

Law Adjunct Professor Dr. Ram Babu Dhakal focused on the lack of institutional development, lack of IP expert in Nepal making a comparison with foreign countries like the USA. So the government should focus on providing qualitative services to its citizens via institutional development since the role of government is a very crucial and significant one in this context.¹³²

12 Experiences.

This question was not mandatory one so only 18 of the respondents have responded. Most of the 18 respondents experienced confusion due to trademark infringement

¹²⁵ Consumer Protection Act, Chapter 9 (2075).

¹²⁶ Consumer Protection Act, Section 58, (2075).

¹²⁷ Consumer Protection Act, Section 25, (2075).

¹²⁸ Consumer Protection Act, Section 27, 28, (2075).

¹²⁹ Consumer Protection Act, Section 35, (2075).

¹³⁰ Supra, Baniya 110.

¹³¹ Supra, Tiwari 119.

¹³² Supra, Dhakal 122.

and felt cheated while buying shoes, clothes, electronic items, cosmetic products, food etc.

Some of the responses are listed below:

- a. One of the respondent's mother bought bulk of shampoo at extremely lower price from some random street vendor 5/6 years ago. Since the price was so cheap she did not check the trademark and bought it, just to find out later that she bought fake product. The product was named "head & shampoo" instead of "head & shoulder". The next day the respondent and her mother went to return the fake product but the shop wasn't there. Then they had to use it anyway, since the product was a cheap knockoff its quality was not good at all. Hence, the respondent's mother got bamboozled.

Here, the respondent's mother had to be smart enough to check the trademark of the product she was buying being extra careful because the vendor was selling them at a very cheap price. The trademark infringed products exist everywhere in the world so the consumers have their duty to carefully check the product before they buy it rather than only blaming the vendors.

- b. Various respondents got confused by the seller while buying shoes, clothes, electronic items, cosmetic products, food. Some of the experiences shared by the respondents are:

- *I bought the Puma outerwear thinking it was branded one from one of the Newroad shop but later I found it was just a fake logo sticker attached to it.*
- *Purchased a Nike shoe with a Nike logo at relatively high price. But later I found it was a fake product with fake branding.*
- *I have bought fake makeup products. Similarly, I have purchased fake potato chips, soaps, pencils things like this. I didn't take any action due to not knowing laws but now I am aware about it and would definitely take necessary action if such things again happen with me.*
- *I got duplicate laptop charger and battery.*

- *So, once I went to buy a Nike Jordan that's very popular. I paid almost 11 thousand Nepalese rupees but alas it was a duplicate first copy. However, I couldn't complain to anyone because in Nepal I think fake products are imported and sold as an original one.*
- *I bought a smartphone which looks like original but later when I used it, I realized that it is completely fake.*
- *Bought and had "Red Blue" instead of "Red Bull", didn't necessarily complained about it but told the shopkeeper the next time I went to that shop. He said that's what we are supplied and can do nothing about it.*
- *I buy kurkure, turns out its kurure.*

These experiences show that the general public get cheated and confused by the sellers on a regular basis despite the fact that it is prohibited by law. Most of them do not even take any actions against it because taking action feels more like a hassle rather than justice because their voices mostly go unheard by the concerned authorities.

- c. The development of science and technology have eased up the lives of many. Shopping has also become a home based thing to do and so has confusing people in the name of online shopping. Some of the examples of it based on the research are:

- *Once I did online shopping from my fb ID, but the size of shoe is smaller than my size, when I call to complain about my size they replied that, sir, u can visit my store at some location as they said but when I went there the shop was closed. I feel cheated from them.*
- *Mostly in online stores, products are very different from the description and expenses.*

Hypothesis Testing.

It is hypothesized that trademark infringed products increase confusion in consumers.

The results of the survey taken by the researcher shows that only 21.5% i.e. 25 of the 116 respondents have not purchased duplicate products thinking it was real but the rest of the 78.5% i.e. 88 of the respondents have purchased duplicate product thinking it was real. This result shows that confusion among the consumers led them to make a purchase of the fake products, otherwise no one would willingly buy a fake product spending enough money to purchase a real one.

The research also shows that the existence of trademark infringement has caused confusion in following sectors:

Food 39

Clothes and Shoes 68

Medicine 21

Beauty products 2

Electronics 1

Others 2

Nowhere 1

Hence, **the result of the survey shows affirmative reaction to hypothesis.**

CHAPTER - VI

FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Findings

The study was conducted for fulfillment of academic purpose and the researcher upon the research done with primary as well as secondary sources of data and study materials have found out during the study are presented in the following points;

There is existence of trademark infringed goods all over the world and it affects the consumers if they are not conscious and clever while shopping. Existence of TM infringed goods despite the presence of laws against it is a fact but the trademark infringed goods exist in the market for two main reasons:

- 1) For businessman to earn money through duplicate and trademark infringed goods,
- 2) For the consumers because of their economic standard i.e. most of the consumers do not have a very high income due to which they rely on the affordable/cheap duplicate trademark infringed goods.

The existing laws to address the issues of the seminar are PDT Act, 2022, Consumer Protection Act, 2075. The consumer protection act is a new one which is why it has sufficient and progressive provisions. However, question arises when we talk about its implementation. For example; provision of consumer court, establishment of local committees, implementation of provisions of compensation, punishments are really questionable.

The PDT Act, 2022 BS is rather an old act which does not include the required new provisions in the field of trademark. But again the existing provisions of the act have not been fully utilized.

5.2 Conclusion

The seminar report prepared by the researcher was to find out how much the TM infringed goods are affecting the general public and how much has been done by the concerned authorities to mitigate the problems being created by such infringement.

Trademark infringement is the unauthorized use of a trademark or service mark on or in connection with goods and/or services in a manner that is likely to cause confusion, deception, or mistake about the source of the goods and/or services.¹³³ History reveals that both trademark and consumer laws were evolved with the sole aim of protecting consumers and safeguarding consumers' interest.

The researcher upon research has found out that the trademark infringement exists in every part of the world, the only difference about its regulation is the awareness amongst the buyers, sellers about the existing laws and their rights and the degree of implementation of the laws regarding the topic. The level of awareness of general public is greatly affected by their economic capacity to buy. Trademark infringed goods are helping economically challenged people to wear, eat, drink and live their life based on their economic status. But use of such TM infringed goods can directly affect the health of the consumers causing more economic burden to them. The consumers being deceived and not speaking about it because of their lack of awareness of laws, their rights, procedural hassle shows that the condition of consumers in Nepal is very pathetic and no one is doing anything to improve the situation.

5.3 Suggestions

The paper sums up the effects of TM infringement among general public. Some of the suggestions to the consumers and government regarding the implementation of the laws for better protection of TM infringement can be listed below:

For Government.

1. Many countries follow 'first to file' rule, so the business persons need to be smart and register the product under their name before somebody else does and have enough evidence to prove the ownership.
2. Create proper awareness to the sellers as well as consumers regarding the their rights and duties.

¹³³ United States Patent and Trademark Office, About Trademark Infringement, <https://www.uspto.gov/page/about-trademark-infringement> (accessed on 12th August, 2022).

3. Be prepared to take legal action over trademark infringement. Weigh up whether taking legal action will be worth the expense, but be prepared to pursue offenders for infringement where necessary.
4. The concerned authorities shall try to protect as far as they can and inspect the infringement promptly which would help to develop faith in them.
5. Implement the provisions mentioned in the existing laws like; consumer courts, local consumers' committees etc.
6. Proper implementations of the existing laws and introduce essential laws swiftly.

For Individuals.

1. Only creating a property using creativity is not enough but advertising your product as well as protecting it by business persons is a must themselves.
2. The actual owner needs to own some evidence to show their ownership during investigation. So the owner has to prepare some documents which can be presented to prove the ownership.
3. Report to the concerned department when the confusion is created. The owner needs to take legal action to protect their trademark.
4. Every individual should avoid copy/steal/have unauthorized use of the protected trademarks. Such uses are morally and legally wrong.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX I

Questionnaires for Physical and Online Survey.

1. Does the brand matter to you while you shop? (Includes clothes, food and other products as well]
2. Can you distinguish the real and fake products?
3. How often do you try to get information about products you purchase for your consumption?
4. As a consumer, where have you faced more confusion?
5. Have you ever purchased duplicate products thinking its real? [if your answer is never then skip to Q.no 8]
6. If yes, to whom did you complain? [would really appreciate if you answer the last question as well.]
7. If you did not take action, then why not?
8. Are you aware of the laws related to protection of consumers and trademark in Nepal?
9. Let us suppose, you are a business person in Nepal, how safe would you feel the Nepalese market for protection of your trademark (TM)?
10. Do you think you or someone you know can easily copy the Trademark (TM) existing in Nepalese market and get away with it?
11. How effective do you think are the laws of trademark and consumer protection in Nepal?
12. What do you think are the reasons behind lack of law enforcement of trademark and consumer related issues?
13. What do you think is the role of the government for protection of such infringement?
14. If you have any experiences related to the topic like if you have been deceived by the shopkeepers, please feel free to share briefly. [Please mention your email too if not mentioned above]